

Semiprime Factorization Algorithm For Quantum Computers Enabling Parallelization

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Abstract

A quantum computer is considered to be superior to a classical computer at performing certain computations. This study proposes an algorithm in which a quantum computer assists a classical computer to perform a significant amount of computations quickly. This gives rise to a computer architecture where the capabilities of a classical and quantum computer are harnessed to solve difficult problems. This paper gives an iterative approach for extracting information from a quantum computer. The proposed algorithm applies core concepts from Deutsch-Jozsa algorithm to solve problems on semiprime factorization in polynomial time. It also shows how quantum computers can significantly speed up a specific form of the ordered search problem.

keywords

Semiprime factorization , binary search , algorithms , number theory , phase quick back , constant functions , interference

1 Introduction

In the 1930s the Church-Turing Thesis was developed by Turing and Church [1] [2] , enabling us to distinguish between computable and non-computable functions. The thesis shows that any function which can be computed by an effective method can be computed on a Turing machine. However, the terms computable and non-computable were insufficient because it is necessary to know the efficiency of how functions can be computed. The Cobham-Edmonds thesis developed by Alan Cobham and Jack Edmonds shows a problem can be efficiently solved if a polynomial time algorithm can solve the problem [3] [4]. The concept of time complexity enables us to classify algorithms into Polynomial (P) and Nondeterministic Polynomial classes (NP). The NP class problems usually require a

significant amount of time , space and computational power to solve , but their solutions can be verified in polynomial time. If it is assumed that $P \neq NP$, there are certain problems in the NP classes which are not NP-complete [5] . This research would focus on the semiprime factorization problem which is one of the problems in the NP class that is not NP-complete.

The semiprime factorization is a difficult problem , but this study gives an algorithm which makes it easier to factorize large semiprimes if the number of the digits of any of the prime factors of the semiprime is known. The algorithm requires a unique type of computer architecture where a classical computer can quickly compile instructions for a quantum computer. The proposed semiprime factorization algorithm is an iterative algorithm which sequentially reveals digits of another composite number that shares a common divisor with the semiprime to be factored such that the common divisor is greater than one. The algorithm also enables parallelization and it could possibly require lesser amount of qubits compared to Shor's algorithm. This paper gives an instance where quantum computers significantly speed up the ordered search problem using a modified form of the the binary search algorithm.

Binary search is an ancient algorithm which is commonly applied to the ordered search problems on sorted arrays. It used to find a target element in a sorted array by continuously halving the search area until the target element is found. The first published discussion on binary search is attributed to John Mauchly [6] during his Moore School lectures , but in 1962 Hermann Bottenbruch published an ALGOL 60 implementation which improved on issues with the previous implementations of the algorithm [7] . Then later Anthony Lin published a review on the history and implementations of the binary search algorithm [8]

The rest of the paper would be organized as follows in section §2 we discuss Quantum computation , in section §3 we give our proposed semiprime factorization algorithm and the subroutines of the algorithms , section §3 also gives the correctness and the computational complexity of the algorithm. In section §4 the process of parallelization is discussed. In section §5 The comments and problems about the algorithm is discussed. Section §6 Discusses areas where future work can be done

2 Quantum Computing

The model of quantum computing was introduced in 1980 by Benioff [9]. Quantum computers outperform classical computers in solving certain problems because quantum algorithms can take advantage of certain laws of quantum mechanics such as superposition , interference and entanglement. In the field of quantum computing qubits are used to store information and the Dirac notation is used to describe quantum states. The principle of superposition enables qubits to exist in a linear combination of states and this gives

quantum computers the ability to work with exponentially many possibilities at once.

Quantum computers use quantum gates to perform operations on qubits and these quantum gates are unitary operators acting on qubits. Quantum gates can be combined to form the universal quantum gates, which can be used to construct quantum circuits. Quantum gate arrays can be applied to qubits in a specific sequence to perform computations on a quantum computers. However, the laws of quantum mechanics requires operations in quantum computers to be reversible. This makes computation on quantum computers more complicated, but this does not hinder quantum computers from computing irreversible functions. Bennett showed that irreversible computations can be made reversible by storing extra information in the computer [10]. This enables quantum computers to perform computations reversibly.

Quantum algorithms provide easy solutions to certain problems that classical computers cannot easily solve. However, the implementation of these algorithms has faced many issues due to the limitations in the current quantum computing hardware. For example, the qubits currently available require error correction because they are susceptible to noise from their environment. In this paper we would apply concepts from Deutsch-Jozsa algorithm [11], Shor's algorithm [12] and Grover's algorithm [13] to design an algorithm for factoring semiprimes. The Deutsch-Jozsa algorithm enables a quantum computer to determine if a function is balanced or constant in a single query whereas a classical computer running a deterministic algorithm requires $2^{n-1} + 1$ queries to solve this problem in the worst case [11].

Another notable quantum algorithm is Shor's algorithm which was the first algorithm to show that integers can be factored in polynomial time on a quantum computer [12]. Shor's algorithm reduces the problem of integer factorization to a problem of order-finding and it solves the problem using the quantum phase estimation algorithm.

Grover's algorithm provides quadratic speed up for quantum computers retrieving items from an unordered database compared to classical computers [13]. This algorithm made researchers to study the efficiency of quantum computers in searching ordered lists to determine if quantum computers were significantly better than classical computers at the ordered search problem. According to Buhrman et al [14], quantum computers do not offer significant speed up to the ordered search problem as they do for unstructured search problem. Hoyer et al [15] have shown quantum computers can at most offer a constant-factor speed up to the ordered search problem. However, this may not completely be true in the case of our proposed algorithm because the quantum computer quickly examines numbers within an ordered range significantly faster than classical computers can search.

3 Algorithm

3.1 Problem Setup

Given a semiprime number N such that $N = pq$, where p and q are prime numbers, $p > q$ and the numbers of digits of p and q are known in advance, the task is to determine the primes p and q such that $N = pq$.

3.2 High level Idea

The proposed algorithm comprises of seven subroutines and it requires a computer architecture which a classical computer can quickly convert a high-level quantum program into instructions that the quantum computer can execute. The algorithm reduces the problem of integer factorization to a decision problem where a quantum computer assists a classical computer to check through an ordered interval of numbers. The decision problem involves deciding if a function is constant or not and this enables the classical computer to narrow down a range of values. Similar to the Deutsch-Jozsa algorithm [11], the classical computer decides based on the effect of interference on the probability amplitudes and relative phases introduced by the phase kickback mechanism. However, we use the euclidean algorithm in place of the black box function in the Deutsch-Jozsa algorithm because, the euclidean algorithm gives one as a result for the greatest common divisor of two numbers that are coprime. This makes the algorithm only suitable for factoring semiprimes.

Similar to Shor's algorithm [12], the proposed algorithm also uses modular arithmetic in the quantum computing subroutine to create an interference pattern over a range of inputs, but the algorithm does not require modular exponentiation. The algorithm uses the known amount of digits of either prime factor for the given semiprime to estimate the interval of numbers that share a common divisor with the semiprime to be factored, then the algorithm implements a modified form of the binary search algorithm to determine the digits of another number that shares a common divisor with the semiprime to be factored. This number is usually one digit greater than the semiprime.

3.3 Core Subroutines

The algorithm comprises of seven subroutines. The first two subroutines are initializations and they are not actively involved in the main loop for the algorithm. The subroutines of the algorithm are executed sequentially until the decision subroutine because the decision subroutine initiates a main loop for the algorithm. The main loop in the algorithm loops from the decision subroutine back to the estimation of resulting subinterval subroutine several times. From the decision subroutine, the algorithm loops back to the estimation of

resulting subinterval subroutine , then it moves to the Quantum Compilation subroutine , next to the Quantum computation subroutine until it reaches the Decision subroutine. The decision subroutine only breaks the loop when the interval of the range is less than three , then it moves to the factorization subroutine.

3.3.1 Constant Definition

In this subroutine the classical computer determines the constant terms to be used in the other subroutines. This subroutine takes input N which is the semiprime to be factored and it also takes input L which is the number of digits for any of the prime factors of the semiprime.

```

1: function CONSTANTS( $N, L$ )
2:    $S = 2$ 
3:    $R = N \pmod{S}$ 
4:    $L -= 1$ 
5:   Semiprime_string = CONVERT_TO_STRING( $N$ )
6:    $S\_L = \text{LENGTH}(\text{Semiprime\_string})$ 
7:   return  $S, L, R, S\_L, N$ 
8: end function

```

The pseudocode above gives a function `CONSTANTS` which starts by initializing S as integer two. The value of S would be two throughout this algorithm. The value two is selected because it can be used to estimate a suitable interval of numbers sharing a common divisor with semiprime N such that the numbers in the interval are not large. Then the function `CONSTANTS` calculates integer R which is the remainder obtained from dividing N by S . Next the constant one is subtracted from L because the value of $(L - 1)$ would be used in the next subroutine. Then we cast variable N which is an integer to a string in order to determine the number of digits of semiprime N using the `Length` function. The obtained length is stored in the variable S_L , then the function `CONSTANTS` returns S , L , R , S_L and N . The modular arithmetic operation can be easily performed by a classical computer so the cost of computing the constants does not dominate the time complexity of this algorithm.

3.3.2 INTERVAL ESTIMATION

In this subroutine the classical computer estimates the interval of numbers sharing common divisors with semiprime N using our knowledge of the number of digits of any prime factor of semiprime N . Then we determine a range of numbers such that the difference between the highest and lowest term in the range is the estimated interval . This is in

attempt to make it possible to find only one number sharing a common divisor with N in the range of numbers. The outputs S , L , R , S.L and N from the constant definition subroutine are taken as inputs for the function INTERVAL in this subroutine.

```

1: function INTERVAL(S, L, S.L, R, N)
2:   SET Nines To ""
3:   DECLARE integer
4:   DECLARE interval
5:   DECLARE init_ceiling
6:   DECLARE init_floor
7:   for i = 1 → L do
8:     SET Nines TO Nines + "9"
9:   end for
10:  SET integer TO STRING_TO_INT(NINES)
11:  interval = S*integer
12:  init_floor = 10S.L
13:  init_ceiling= init_floor + interval
14:  Return N , S , R, interval , init_ceiling , init_floor
15: end function

```

Through our knowledge of the digits either prime factor of the semiprime N has , the closest valid number can estimated by choosing another number such that all it's digits have a numeric value of nine and this number has one digit less than the number of digits of the prime factor of N to be estimated. This was why one was subtracted from input L in the previous subroutine. The pseudocode above determines the close estimate using a for loop which stores a string of the integer value nine in a variable defined as Nines based on the value of L obtained from the constant definition subroutine. Then we cast the resulting string Nines into an integer data type which we store in the variable integer. The variable integer is our close estimate of the prime factor to the semiprime . In the pseudocode the interval of the numbers sharing a common divisor with N is approximated by taking the product of variable integer and input S from the constant definition subroutine . Then the value of input S.L is used to determine the initial range of numbers to be checked. All the selected range of numbers are all one digit greater than the semiprime N to be factored . The lower limit of the range is obtained in the pseudocode by finding the value of ten raised to the power of input S.L , then the result is stored in the variable init_floor. The upper limit of the range is obtained by adding the lower limit to the estimated interval. Then the value obtained for the upper limit is stored in the variable init_ceiling.

3.3.3 Estimation of resulting subinterval

In this subroutine a classical computer is used to determine the actual range of values that the quantum computer would check. The constant S would be used to narrow down the amount of terms in the selected range $\text{init_floor} \rightarrow \text{init_ceiling}$ into a fewer amount of terms with a higher chance of sharing a common divisor with semiprime N . We are able to narrow down the amount of terms in the selected range because a sequence of numbers that share a common divisor with semiprime N form an arithmetic progression whose common difference is given by the product of constant S and either of the primes. The estimated interval used in the proposed algorithm should be lesser than the common difference since our approximation of the factor is one digit lesser than the actual prime factor of semiprime N . The implication is that there can be at most two unique numbers sharing a common divisor with N in the selected range, meaning we can have either two, one or none of such unique numbers in the range. It is possible that two unique terms lie in the range because both prime factors of N can form two separate progressions such that the n th term for both sequences fall within the range $\text{init_floor} \rightarrow \text{init_ceiling}$ and it is only possible if both factors have a very small difference. The unique number sharing a common factor with N must also be congruent to $N \pmod{S}$ since the common difference is a multiple of S . Next, we determine the amount of terms congruent to $N \pmod{S}$ in our selected range using the variable init_floor and init_ceiling which we determined from our interval estimation subroutine. This is determined by equating the expression $S(X)+R$ to the init_ceiling and init_floor , where X is the variable. The variable X represents the new lower and upper bound in the pseudocode below.

```
1: list = [0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0]
2: function AMOUNT OF TERMS( S, R, interval, init_ceiling, init_floor)
3:   LowerBound = (init_floor - R)/S
4:   UpperBound = (init_ceiling - R)/S
5:   SubInterval = ( UpperBound - LowerBound )
6:   NoTerms = ROUND(SubInterval)
7:   NoTerms += 1
8:   Lower = FLOOR(LowerBound)
9:   list[0] = init_floor
10:  list[1] = init_ceiling
11:  list[2] = interval
12:  list[3] = S
13:  list[4] = R
14:  list[5] = N
15:  Return Lower, NoTerms, interval, R, S
16: end function
```

In the pseudocode above we start by initializing all the elements of a list as zero and the total number of elements is usually six. The function Amount Of Terms in the pseudocode above determines the amount of terms of the algebraic expression $S(X)+R$ that fall between the range `init_floor` and `init_ceiling`. Where X is the only variable. It also estimates the least possible value of X in the expression $S(X)+R$ that fall within the range `init_floor` to `init_ceiling`. Then the function returns the number of terms as `NoTerms` and it returns the minimum value of X in the range as `Lower`. The function returns `Lower`, `NoTerms`, `interval`, `S`, `R`. The value one is added to the `NoTerms` variable to avoiding skipping any terms since the `Floor` function was used with the minimum value of X . The current value of the `init_floor`, `init_ceiling`, `R`, `S`, `N` and `interval` also have to stored in memory of the classical computer because we cannot easily recover their values from the quantum computers the way it is done on a classical computer. In the pseudocode above a list data structure is used to store their current values. This was why the list with six elements was initialized with zero for all the elements at the begin of the pseudocode above.

3.3.4 Quantum Compilation

Classical computers can be used to compile code for quantum computers from high level languages into low-level quantum circuits and pulses. This process is referred to as quantum compilation. This subroutine involves programming the quantum computer to execute sequential arithmetic operations on qubits in superposition based on the the outputs obtained from the subroutine for estimation of resulting subinterval. The task is to compile a quantum circuit that can execute $\gcd([S([K \bmod (NoTerms + 1)] + Lower) + R], N)$. This enables us to determine the greatest common divisors that exists between the semiprime N and each term within the range `LowerBound` and `UpperBound`. Where K is a variable which represents the value stored in an input register whose qubits are in superposition. Deutsch [16] showed that any function that can be computed on a classical computer can also be computed on a quantum computer. This implies that the function $\gcd([S([K \bmod (NoTerms + 1)] + Lower) + R], N)$ should be computable by a quantum computer. The ability to compute the function for z qubits in superposition is important in the next subroutine of this algorithm. This is because the resulting value for any interval with no unique number sharing a common divisor with N behaves similar to a constant function. This can be attributed to a unique property of the euclidean algorithm which gives one as the result for two numbers that are coprime. However, the maximum binary value that z qubits in the input register can represent must exceed $(NoTerms + 1)$ such that it enables repetition of the greatest common divisors of all the terms between `LowerBound` and `UpperBound`. In the next subroutine we give a way to easily determine if the function is constant, by applying a sequence of Logical OR operations followed by

a single Logical AND operation using the universal quantum gates. Now we would break down the major arithmetic operations in sub stages.

- Modular arithmetic : $K \bmod (\text{NoTerms} + 1)$ This expression involves modular arithmetic with a precomputed constant $(\text{NoTerms} + 1)$. The expression makes the function appear complicated because a lot of division operations has to be performed to calculate the remainder of the values of K divided by the constant $(\text{NoTerms} + 1)$. The Newton-Raphson Method developed by Newton [17] and Raphson [18] can be applied to optimize division operations by approximating reciprocals of the quotient. In this case we could precompute the reciprocal of constant $(\text{NoTerms} + 1)$ to a sufficient degree of precision to convert the division operations into multiplication operations so the precomputed reciprocal can be used for multiple division operations with the constant quotient $(\text{NoTerms} + 1)$. This would enable the division operation to parallelized because multiplication involves parallel addition. We can use the quotient approximated to determine the remainder, but it must be implemented reversibly. In this way we can attempt to combat the problem of decoherence by computing our results faster. Methods such as the restoring division cannot be parallelized so they might not scale and they could be too slow. The computational complexity of the modular arithmetic is $O(n^2)$ using the modified Newton- Raphson Method. This is because we have to perform two multiplication operations using long-hand multiplication followed by a subtraction operation. The computational complexity for long-hand multiplication is $O(n^2)$ while the cost of the subtraction operation is $O(n)$.

- Multiplication : The values required for the multiplication operation should not grow too large since the large values would be reduced by the optimized modular arithmetic operation. For multiplication there is no single best algorithm so we adopt the long-hand elementary multiplication. It has a computational complexity $O(n^2)$ for classical computers so the computational complexity for the long-hand multiplication on quantum computers should asymptotically be $O(n^2)$.

Multiplying by S in this function should be easier since the value of S is fixed as constant two in this algorithm. This is because multiplying by two in binary is just a left shift so no carry operation is required to multiply by S . This can be implemented using CNOT gates and an additional ancillary register to make it reversible. This is one of the reasons the value two was chosen as the value of constant S

- Euclidean algorithm : The computational complexity for the Euclidean algorithm on quantum computers using longhand division should asymptotically be $O(n^2)$. This should be true because the computational complexity of the euclidean algo-

rithm for classical computers using longhand division is $O(n^2)$. The aspect that might be challenging would be computing it reversibly . The euclidean algorithm requires dealing with remainders which might not be too difficult because quantum computers always store additional inputs to make computation reversible.

In this subroutine we compile a high level program which enables the Quantum computer to execute the function $\text{gcd}([S([K \bmod (\text{NoTerms} + 1)] + \text{Lower}) + R], N)$. Since it can be computed classically , There should be a quantum gate array to implement this function. We compile the optimized quantum circuit with our constants and precomputed value of reciprocal of $(\text{NoTerms} + 1)$.

3.3.5 Quantum Computation

In this subroutine the quantum computer evaluates the function $\text{gcd}([S([K \bmod (\text{NoTerms} + 1)] + \text{Lower}) + R], N)$ through the low-level circuit compiled in the quantum compilation subroutine. This low level circuit is a quantum gate array. The hadamard gates is used to set the qubits of the input register with z qubits in a state of superposition. Then the quantum gate array is used to evaluate the function , taking variable K to be the binary values represented by the input register's qubits in superposition. The intermediate results obtained during computation can be stored in sufficiently large ancillary registers. If the selected range does not contain a unique number that shares a common divisor with semiprime N , the function behaves similar to a constant function where all the outputs are one. So it forms an interference pattern which can be easily determined. Whereas if the selected range is a unique range containing at least one number that shares a common divisor with the semiprime , the gcd function can only give either value one and a prime factor or value one and two prime factors. In the case of a unique range sharing a common divisor , the least significant qubit in the output register should always be in the computational basis state $|1\rangle$ since all prime numbers are positive odd integers and the last digit of all positive odd integers represented in binary should be one. Hence , for the possible outputs that the gcd function can give in this case , the least significant qubit of the output register should always be in basis state $|1\rangle$. This makes it easier to know if the function is constant or not by using a circuit that can enable us to easily determine if only the least significant qubit is in the computational basis state $|1\rangle$

The circuit determines if only the least significant qubit of the output register is in the basis state $|1\rangle$ or any other qubit of the output register is also in basis state $|1\rangle$. It determines this by performing a sequence of logical OR operations on all the output register's qubits excluding the least significant qubit , followed by the logical AND operation of the result with the least significant qubit in the output register.

Figure 1: Quantum Gates Implementing Logical OR

INPUT A	INPUT B	OUTPUT C
0	0	0
0	1	1
1	0	1
1	1	1

Table 1: Truth table for OR gate

The circuit diagram in figure 1 above gives the reversible implementation of the logical OR operation on inputs A and B using the Toffoli and CNOT gate. The circuit determines logical OR operation by executing logical operation $A \text{ (AND) } B \text{ (XOR) } B \text{ (XOR) } A$. Then the value of the OR operation is stored in the ancillary register C. The truth table for the OR logical operation is given in Table 1

Figure 2: Toffoli Gate Implementing Logical AND

INPUT A	INPUT B	OUTPUT C
0	0	0
0	1	0
1	0	0
1	1	1

Table 2: Truth table for Logical AND

The circuit diagram in figure 2 gives the reversible implementation of the Logical AND operation on inputs A and B using the Toffoli quantum gate. The truth table for

the logical AND operation is given in Table 2 . Then the result is stored in ancillary qubit C

Figure 3: combined circuit diagram

The circuit diagram in figure 3 gives the quantum circuit which can be used to determine if only the least significant qubit of a three qubit register is in the basis state $|1\rangle$ specifically in our problem. The variables A , B and C represents the basis states of a three bit register where C is the least significant bit. The qubits D and E are ancillary registers and the result of the whole unitary operation can be obtained through E .

Qubit A	Qubit B	Qubit C	Ancillary D	Output E
0	0	0	0	0
0	0	1	0	0
0	1	0	1	0
0	1	1	1	1
1	0	0	1	0
1	0	1	1	1
1	1	0	1	0
1	1	1	1	1

Figure 4: Truth table for combined circuit

The truth table in figure 4 shows that when the basis state of the output register is $|011\rangle$, $|101\rangle$ and $|111\rangle$ the combined circuit in Figure 3 gives a distinct output on E from the basis state $|001\rangle$. Where the least significant qubit of the output register is always in the computational basis state $|1\rangle$. It can be observed on the table in Figure 4 that the combined circuit in Figure 3 gives zero on output E when only the least significant qubit C is in the basis state one , but for all other possibilities where the least significant qubit must be in computational basis state one output E always gives one. Hence output E simplifies the decision problem with the obtained distinct values. This shows that the method of using OR operations followed by one AND operation should be applicable no matter how size of the output register.

This circuit assists to simplify the problem because in our case there are only three possible results since one of the inputs of the gcd() function is a semiprime and the

other input is not a multiple of the semiprime. The answer must either give one or any of the prime factors and for the three results the least significant qubit must be in the basis state $|1\rangle$. This is because both prime factors are positive odd integers and for any positive odd integer in binary to be odd, the least significant qubit should always be in computational basis state $|1\rangle$. In this subroutine the main aim is to identify if a selected range has at least one unique number sharing a common divisor with N or if there is no unique number in the range. So we group the possibility where the selected range is a unique range which has one or two of such unique numbers as one case where the function is not constant. While we consider the other possibility where the selected range does not have any unique number sharing a common divisor with N as the case where the function is constant. We can combine the possibility of obtaining one or two unique numbers because the combined circuit in figure 3 or its equivalent gives the same results for all prime numbers as long as the prime number is greater than one. If the selected range does not have a number sharing a common divisor with the semiprime, the $\text{gcd}()$ function gives one as the output for all the values K in superposition and this makes output E to remain in the basis state $|0\rangle$. The range behaves similar to a constant function and it can be easily identified by applying the phase kick back mechanism to output E . The other case can also be determined where we pick a unique range which has at least one number that shares a common divisor with the semiprime N . In this case the $\text{gcd}()$ can either give results one and a prime factor of N or results one and two prime factors periodically due to the effect of the modular arithmetic operation. This makes the output E to be in a superposition of values $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$, producing a destructive interference pattern which can be easily detected through the phase kick back mechanism. The interference redistributes probability amplitudes, enabling us to detect the presence of the relative phase introduced by the phase kick back mechanism. This makes the effect of the interference pattern in the unique range to become observable through measurement probabilities. The phase quick back mechanism gives a different effect in the first case where the selected range acts as a constant function because the output E would remain in the basis state $|0\rangle$ which does not introduce any relative phase. As a result of this we should always obtain zero after measurement in the case of the constant range. This makes it easy to determine if there is a number which shares a common factor with semiprime N in a selected range by applying the phase quick back mechanism to output E . So to easily determine if the function is constant the combined circuit or its equivalent has to be applied to the output register which is superposition of all the outputs of the function, then the phase quick back mechanism is applied to output E of the combined circuit.

It is important to be able to distinguish between both cases of the outputs, but in order to make it easier the the input register needs to be just sufficiently large to produce a periodic interference pattern with repeated outputs from the modulo operation. The

maximum binary value the input register can represent must be much greater than the constant $(NoTerms + 1)$ to create periodic interference patterns for the unique ranges .

3.3.6 Decision

This subroutine updates the search range and interval based on the outcome obtained from the quantum computer. It interprets measurements of probability amplitudes obtained from the quantum computation subroutine to determine if the function is constant or not , then it executes a specific sequence of instructions in each situation. The instructions to be executed in each case would be discussed in two sections

- CONSTANT

If the function is constant there is no unique number sharing a common divisor with N in the range which was checked in the quantum computation subroutine. The pseudocode below uses the current value of `init_floor` , `init_ceiling` , `interval` , S and R stored in the list from the estimation of resulting subinterval to update the search range.

```

1: init_floor = list[0]
2: init_ceiling = list[1]
3: interval = list[2]
4: S = list[3]
5: R = list[4]
6: N = list[5]
7: init_floor = init_floor + interval
8: init_ceiling = init_floor + interval
9: // Return To The Estimation Of Resulting Subinterval subroutine with the updated
   values init_floor and init_ceiling
10: AMOUNT OF TERMS(S, R, interval, init_ceiling, init_floor)

```

In the pseudocode above we move to the next range by adding the present value of variable `interval` to `init_floor` , then the new `init_ceiling` is determined with the updated `init_floor` by adding `init_floor` again to the current `interval`. After updating the `init_floor` and `init_ceiling` the next instruction returns to the estimation of resulting subinterval subroutine where the current `interval` , the updated `init_floor` , updated `init_ceiling` and the constants S , R are passed as inputs to the function Amount of terms.

- NOT CONSTANT This implies that there is at least one unique number sharing a common divisor with Semiprime N in the selected range such that the common

divisor is greater than one. So we divide the interval by two and update `init_ceiling`. In this part of the decision subroutine we implement a modified form of binary search to obtain the digits of one specific unique number in the range. The effect of continuously halving the interval makes both terms to eventually end up on one half of a search range, then from that point the first range we start diving gives the digit of that single unique number in that range. This should be true because the difference that exist between both possible unique terms is a multiple of S which would be greater than one. The psuedocode below implements the binary search by updating the search range from the values of `init_floor`, `init_ceiling`, `interval`, S , N and R stored in the list to update the search range.

```

1: init_floor = list[0]
2: init_ceiling = list[1]
3: interval = list[2]
4:  $S$  = list[3]
5:  $R$  = list[4]
6:  $N$  = list[5]
7: if interval < ( $S + 1$ ) then
8:   // MOVE TO the Factorization subroutine with the current value of init_floor,
   init_ceiling,  $S$ ,  $R$ ,  $N$ 
9:   FACTORIZATION(init_floor, init_ceiling,  $S$ ,  $R$ ,  $N$ )
10: else
11:   interval = CEIL(interval/2)
12:   init_floor = init_floor
13:   init_ceiling = init_floor +interval
14:   // GO TO Subroutine Estimation Of Resulting Subinterval
15:   AMOUNT OF TERMS( $S$ ,  $R$ , interval, init_ceiling, init_floor)
16: end if

```

The modified binary search which the semiprime factorization algorithm implements enables us to narrow down the search range until the search range shrinks. This make the algorithm an iterative algorithm which gradually converges towards the target number in the range sharing a common divisor with the semiprime to be factored. After the first time the algorithm finds a unique range, it takes at most eight iterations from the decision subroutine to the subroutine for estimation of resulting subinterval to obtain a digit of the number sharing common divisor in the range. It is easily observable because after some iterations the digits of `init_ceiling` and `init_floor` start to coincide from the most significant digit to the least significant digit as the interval gradually shrinks. Then to stop the loop initiated by the

decision subroutine a condition is set in the algorithm to move to the Factorization subroutine when the interval is less than $(S+1)$. This is because at this stage there can only be one possible term in the range since the difference between two successive terms $[S(X + 1) + R] - [S(X) + R]$ is S . The unique number can easily be recovered at this stage because there can only be at most two terms (of expression $S(X) + R$ and one of them must be the valid term sharing a common divisor with semiprime N) within an interval S .

3.3.7 Factorization

In this subroutine we determine the precise value of both factors of the semiprime using a classical computer. This is achieved using the high precision estimate of the unique number sharing a common divisor. The interval is not greater than S so there can only be one valid term in the narrowed range. The classical computer determines this valid term of the expression $S(X)+R$ using the function factorization. The function starts by determining the UpperBound, LowerBound and number terms of the expression $S(X)+R$ in the narrowed range, similar to how it was found in the amount of terms function. The number of terms in most cases should be approximately one, but in the pseudocode below we increment the NoTerms variable by 4 to avoid errors from approximation. Then we estimate the smallest integer close to the LowerBound using the floor function and we store the value in variable Lower. The calculated result for Lower is used in a for loop to determine the integer value of the valid term, then the euclidean algorithm is used to calculate the shared common factor between the valid term and the semiprime. The result this subroutine gives are the precise values of the two prime factors of the semiprime N from the input. In case an error occurs the function returns string error

```

1: function FACTORIZATION(init_floor , init_ceiling , S , R ,N)
2:   LowerBound = (init_floor -R) /S
3:   UpperBound = (init_ceiling - R)/S
4:   SubInterval = ( UpperBound-LowerBond )
5:   NoTerms = ROUND(SubInterval)
6:   NoTerms += 4
7:   Lower = FLOOR(LowerBound)
8:   for i=0 → NoTerms do
9:     u = (S*(i+Lower) ) + R
10:    q = gcd(N , u )
11:    if q > 1 then
12:      p = N/q
13:      PRINT p , q
14:      RETURN p , q
15:    end if
16:  end for
17:  RETURN "ERROR"
18: end function

```

3.4 Correctness

This section discusses the proof of concepts used in the Semiprime factorization algorithm works with.

- Lemma : Let $m , n , b , c \in \mathbb{Z}$, with $n \neq 0$

Then

$$(mn + b)c \equiv bc \pmod{n}$$

Proof :

By definition , for integers x , y , we write

$$x \equiv y \pmod{n} \text{ if } n|(x - y)$$

Let

$$X = (mn + b)c , Y = bc$$

Then

$$X - Y = ((mn + b)c) - bc = (mn)c + bc - bc = (mn)c$$

It can be seen that :

$$(mn)c = n(mc)$$

Since : $n|(X - Y)$, by definition $X \equiv Y \pmod{n}$

Hence $(mn + b)c \equiv bc \pmod{n}$

$(mn + b)c$ can be one digit greater than bc if we choose m such that it is large enough. This shows that there would always be a number at least one digit greater than the semiprime to be factored which is congruent to the semiprime modulo n and shares a common factor with the semiprime. In this case c is a common factor to both $c(mn + b)$ and bc

- Lemma let $a, b, n \in \mathbb{Z}$. Then
 $ab \equiv ab + bn \pmod{n}$

Proof : by the definition of congruence modulo n , we have $x \equiv y \pmod{n}$ if $n|(x - y)$.

Consider $(ab + bn) - ab = bn$

Since $b \in \mathbb{Z}$ and $n|bn$ it follows that

$n|(ab + bn) - ab$. Therefore by the definition of congruence
 $ab \equiv ab + bn \pmod{n}$

If ab in the expression $ab = ab + bn \pmod{n}$ is considered a semiprime we can deduce that multiples of bn would form an arithmetic progression $ab + bn$, $ab + 2bn$, $ab + 3bn$ with common difference bn which can be expressed as

$$b(a + n), b(a + 2n), b(a + 3n)$$

Notice that the terms in sequence share a common factor "b" with each other and the semiprime. The semiprime factorization algorithm approximates this common difference using the available partial knowledge about the factors of the semiprime ab . Since we know n is a multiple of the common difference between each term they should all be congruent to $ab \pmod{n}$ because n should be able to divide it's multiples without any remainder.

3.5 Computational Complexity

In this section the computational complexity of the algorithm would be determined. The constant definition subroutine and the interval estimation subroutine can be considered as initializations so their computational complexity can be regarded as $O(1)$ because the algorithm does not iterate through the first two subroutine in the main loop. The computational complexity for the estimation of resulting subinterval subroutine is dominated by two division operations. The Newton-Raphson division algorithm [17] enables division to be implemented in $O(n \log n)$ time complexity. Since the estimation of resulting subinterval subroutine is computed by a classical computer the Newton-Raphson algorithm can be used. This makes the computational complexity $O(2n \log n)$ which just simplifies to $O(n \log n)$.

The computational complexity of the Quantum compilation subroutine is $O(1)$ since it takes constant time to compile code for the quantum computer. The computational

complexity of the subroutine for quantum computation depends on three main operations. The modular arithmetic , multiplication and euclidean algorithm. Using the long hand multiplication the time complexity for multiplication on a quantum computer should asymptotically be $O(n^2)$. The time complexity of the modular arithmetic operation using the modified Newton-Raphson Method is $O(n^2)$. The computational complexity of the euclidean algorithm on the quantum computer should asymptotically be $O(n^2)$. This makes the computational complexity of the quantum computation subroutine $O(3n^2)$ which we consider as $O(n^2)$.

The decision subroutine mostly involves trivial operations. The only significant operation we can account for is the operation of dividing the search interval by two. The computational complexity for the decision subroutine using the Newton-Raphson method is $O(n \log n)$. The time complexity of the factorization subroutine can be considered as $O(1)$ since the amount of iterations cannot exceed four and the subroutine is not involved in the main loop of the algorithm.

The amount of iterations for the main loop usually depends on $2(4n)+11$. Where n is the number of digits of the prime factor of the semiprime. This is because four is the smallest exponent of two which is greater than ten. This implies that the interval must be divided by two at most four times to decrease it's number of digits by one. The constant two multiplying $4n$ accounts for instances in the loop where the target number is in the other half of the divided range. We also add the constant eleven because the estimate of the prime factor is one digit less than it's actual value. This makes the digits of the variables `init_floor` and `init_ceiling` to start coinciding in at most eight successive iterations after the first time we find a unique range. It should only take eleven iterations in the worst case to find a unique range for the first time since our estimate of the prime factor is a digit lesser than the actual prime factor. If we focus only the subroutines that loop which are the estimation of resulting subinterval , Quantum Compilation , Quantum Computation and Decision . The computational complexity can be determined to be $O(8 \log n(n \log n + 1 + n^2 + n \log n) + 11)$ which can be considered as $O(\log n(n^2))$. The computational complexity of the algorithm is $O(n^2 \log n)$.

4 Parallelization

The proposed semiprime factorization algorithm can be modified to support parallelization by dividing the search range into multiple parts to be inspected by multiple quantum computers at once instead of two. In order to achieve it a powerful central classical computer is required which can quickly divide a search range into multiple splits and compile multiple instructions for each quantum computer to execute. The central classical computer should also be able to process outputs from the quantum computers quickly. This reduces the amount of iterations required to converge the search interval and it signifi-

cantly improves the efficiency of the algorithm.

5 Comments and Open Problems

The semiprime factorization algorithm requires a stable quantum computer with sufficient error correction and speed , but the quantum computers that are available are prone to noise from the surroundings. This might affect the implementation of this algorithm because the algorithm requires stable qubits with sufficient precision and error correction.

In addition , the main loop in the algorithm may not be able to recover the last digit of the number sharing a common divisor with the semiprime. This is so because we have to round up , then increment the interval and NoTerms variable to avoid skipping any number , so the interval may never reach zero. The interval in some iterations might be divisible by two and in other iterations it might not be divisible by two . The issue is addressed by stopping the main loop when the interval is less than $(S+1)$ which is 3 in this implementation of this algorithm. The amount of terms can easily be tested by the classical computer because there can only one valid term within a range of interval S . The conditional statement in the decision subroutine that breaks the main loop enables the algorithm to stop because , if the value of the interval eventually gives one , the main loop would never stop. This is because the value of one divided by two is 0.5 which is still approximately one and this creates a repeating cycle.

The computational complexity of this algorithm depends mostly on the number of digits of the prime factor of the semiprime because it directly affects the size of the interval which determines the amount of iterations from the Decision subroutine to the Estimation of resulting subinterval subroutine. After the first time a unique range is found , it takes a maximum of eight successive iterations across the main loop of subroutines to reveal one digit of the number sharing common divisor. It should take at most eleven initial iterations to find a unique range .

This implementation of this algorithm sets the constant S to two because it is the most suitable value of S which would give us the minimal value of to work with and it also enables us to simplify one multiplication operation in the subroutine for quantum computation. In theory we can use a larger value of S but the total amount of terms in the first range would still be the same value . Hence , small values of S are more suitable.

The proposed algorithm could require lesser amount of qubits than Shor's algorithm. This may be the case because the algorithm gives a way to control the size of the initial inputs thus fewer ancillary registers may be required. The algorithm might not also require as many repetition of the output values in the quantum subroutine as Shor's algorithm because the quantum computer only gives two possible results for every computation in the subroutine for quantum computation .In Shor's algorithm a significant amount of repetitions of the periodic structure of modular exponentiation function is required

to obtain a high precision estimate of a rational multiple of the period inverse. In the proposed algorithm we use the phase quick back mechanism to extract information from a quantum computer via interference.

The RSA algorithm developed by Rivest et al [20] and it enables asymmetric key encryption. The security of the RSA algorithm is based on the difficulty of factoring product of primes so the ability of the algorithm to factorize integers in polynomial time might be a threat to the cryptographic algorithm. The algorithm could potentially pose risks to the RSA because the number of bits or digits for the two primes factors of the public key is known.

In addition , showing that semiprimes can be factorized in polynomial time does not mean that P equals NP because the problem is not NP complete. It can only be shown that P equals Np only if a polynomial time algorithm were found for an NP complete problem [21]. The fact that this algorithm can factorize semiprimes in polynomial time makes it suitable for large numbers provided a suitable computer architecture is used to run the algorithm. On a classical computer it would be extremely slow to check a huge range of numbers if any number shares a common divisor with a semiprime because in the worst case , it must check every single number but on a quantum computer it is much easier to determine . This makes it very inefficient to run the quantum computation subroutine on a classical computer because it must find the common divisor in almost every iteration which is the answer to the initial factorization question. This algorithm is structured to find a solution to both problems limiting both classical and quantum computers from solving the semiprime factorization problem. The first problem is the difficulty of extracting information from a quantum computer and the second is that deterministic classical algorithms require exponential time to determine if a function is constant. This algorithm also shows that quantum computers give significant query advantage in this specific form of the ordered search problem where we search if there is a common divisor to a semiprime over a sequence of ordered ranges

This study implies that integrating the classical computers and quantum computers could significantly improve our computational power compared to what the existing computer architectures offers. This could enable classical computers to augment the capabilities of the quantum computers by assisting to extract information from the quantum computer. However , the development of more efficient methods of getting information from the quantum computer might make the integrated computer architecture unnecessary.

6 Future Work

It necessary to design the unique computer architecture which would enable this algorithm to be implemented efficiently. To achieve this there needs to be seamless transition

from the subroutines involving quantum processing and classical processing. Hence , enough research is required to design such computer architecture. Future research needs to be done on ways to implement optimized arithmetic operations on quantum computers because in the algorithm quick responses from the quantum computer are crucial. Sufficient studies and research is also required to develop quantum computers that are more stable and less susceptible to noise from the surroundings.

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